

Subroutine SUN - calculation of the barycentric position of the Sun

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Introduction

The Fortran subroutine SUN calculates the coordinates of the Sun in the equatorial J2000.0 frame for any given time in a 200-day interval from September 1987 to February 1993. The accuracy is better than 1 Mm (max error).

Argument list:

SUBROUTINE SUN(t, r, ierr)

INPUT: t = time from J1988.0 = JD2447162.0 = 1988 Jan 1, 12 h TDT,
[s]. NOTE RESTRICTION IN RANGE BELOW!

OUTPUT: r() = 3-vector containing the components of position in the
equatorial J2000.0 frame, [m]

ierr = 0 on normal return

-1 if t is not in the permitted range (see below)

NOTE 1: t and r are DOUBLE PRECISION (REAL*8)

NOTE 2: $\underline{r} = \underline{0}$ is returned if ierr = -1

Restriction

The time argument (t) must be in the range $-10\ 540\ 800 \leq t < 162\ 259\ 200$,
i.e. $2447040 \leq \text{JD} < 2449040$ or $87/09/01.5 \leq \text{date} < 93/02/21.5$.

Execution time

On HP9000 at Lund Observatory, 0.47 ms per call.

Source

The heliocentric coordinates of the centre of mass of the Sun and five outer planets (Jupiter to Pluto) was tabulated by Clemence (Astron. Papers Am. Ephem. XIII, Pt IV, 1953) for the period 1800-2060 and in intervals of 40 days. For the present purpose, the following modifications to this table was required:

- (i) reversing the sign to get the barycentric coordinates of the Sun;
- (ii) correction of the masses of Saturn and Pluto to modern values;
- (iii) transformation from B1950.0 to J2000.0;
- (iv) conversion from tabular form to analytical approximations.

The masses for Saturn and Pluto used by Clemence differ from the IAU (1976) values as shown below.

	<u>Clemence (1953)</u>	<u>IAU (1976)</u>	<u>modern</u>
Saturn, $1/m_6 =$	3501.6	3498.5	--
Pluto, $1/m_9 =$	360000	$3 \cdot 10^6$	$1.3 \cdot 10^8$

For Pluto, the mass determined from its satellite supersedes the IAU value. To take into account the new masses, the coordinates were corrected by means of the formula,

$$\underline{h}_{\text{corrected}} = 1.0000025137 \underline{h}_{\text{old}} + 0.0000002527 \underline{h}_6 - 0.0000027664 \underline{h}_9$$

where $\underline{h}$ are heliocentric vectors. $\underline{h}_9$ was taken from Eckert et al. (Astron. Papers Am. Ephem. XII, 1951), i.e. the source used by Clemence; $\underline{h}_6$ however was computed with the low-precision formula by Van Flandern and Pulkkinen (Astrophys. J. Suppl. 41, 391, 1979). The corrections may amount to about 0.4 Mm for Saturn and 13 Mm for Pluto.

Transformation to J2000.0 was made with the formula on page S37 of the Astronomical Almanac for 1984.

Finally, a polynomial of degree six was fitted to the 51 tabular points per coordinate (JD2447040.5 to 2449040.5 step 40). The maximum residual of the fit is 0.11 Mm.

A maximum error of about 1 Mm is expected for the final routine. The major contributors are the neglected inner planets (amplitudes 0.01, 0.27, 0.46, and 0.07 Mm, respectively) and the mass of Uranus (0.5 Mm difference between the IAU value and that of DE200).

SUBROUTINE sun(t, r, ierr)

c HIPPARCOS - NDAC - General routines - Sun ephemeris
 c
 c Calculates the Sun's barycentric position at a given time

c Input:

c t = time in seconds from J1988.0 (JD 2447162.0 12h TDT)
 c (-10540800 <= t < 162259200 or 2447040 <= JD < 2449040)

c Output:

c r(i) = barycentric rectangular equatorial coordinates [m]
 c (i = 1 to 3)
 c ierr = 0 on normal return, -1 if t is out of range

c Source: "Coordinates of the Centre of Mass of the Sun and the Five
 c Outer Planets", by G M Clemence (Astron. Papers Am. Ephem.
 c Volume XIII, Part IV.
 c Modified to modern values for the masses of Pluto and
 c Saturn (respectively 1/130,000,000 and 1/3498.5)

c Estimated accuracy: max error < 1 Mm

c Execution time: 0.466 ms per call (HP 9000, Lund Observatory)

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IMPLICIT DOUBLE PRECISION (a-h,o-z)

DIMENSION r(3)

DATA	x0,y0,z0 /	53981700d0,	59006980d0,	18150570d0/,
	x1,y1,z1 /	87051240d0,	28982520d0,	10887590d0/,
	x2,y2,z2 /	-36678210d0,	-80156460d0,	35306020d0/,
	x3,y3,z3 /	-49562930d0,	-24528170d0,	-93451730d0/,
	x4,y4,z4 /	15184800d0,	-17536910d0,	-78893240d0/,
	x5,y5,z5 /	50332880d0,	57300190d0,	23338830d0/,
	x6,y6,z6 /	-28819960d0,	7810805d0,	4050627d0/

IF ((t .GE. -10540800d0) .AND. (t .LT. 162259200d0)) THEN
 t0 = t/1d8 - 0.8d0

r(1) = x0+t0*(x1+t0*(x2+t0*(x3+t0*(x4+t0*(x5+t0*x6))))
 r(2) = y0+t0*(y1+t0*(y2+t0*(y3+t0*(y4+t0*(y5+t0*y6))))
 r(3) = z0+t0*(z1+t0*(z2+t0*(z3+t0*(z4+t0*(z5+t0*z6))))
 ierr = 0

ELSE

r(1) = 0d0
 r(2) = 0d0
 r(3) = 0d0
 ierr = -1

ENDIF

RETURN
 END

TABLE 1. Barycentric coordinates of the Sun calculated with the subroutine SUN

JD	t	r(1)	r(2)	r(3)
2447040.5	-10497600.	-611392920.	486865613.	213175235.
2447080.5	-7041600.	-605287485.	449881522.	197313539.
2447120.5	-3585600.	-596704488.	413694945.	181736741.
2447160.5	-129600.	-585715499.	378472631.	166517990.
2447200.5	3326400.	-572404435.	344369931.	151725848.
2447240.5	6782400.	-556866431.	311530910.	137424312.
2447280.5	10238400.	-539206734.	280088466.	123672836.
2447320.5	13694400.	-519539643.	250164463.	110526366.
2447360.5	17150400.	-497987477.	221869871.	98035371.
2447400.5	20606400.	-474679583.	195304919.	86245887.
2447440.5	24062400.	-449751377.	170559250.	75199558.
2447480.5	27518400.	-423343420.	147712096.	64933691.
2447520.5	30974400.	-395600532.	126832452.	55481307.
2447560.5	34430400.	-366670937.	107979270.	46871203.
2447600.5	37886400.	-336705449.	91201652.	39128019.
2447640.5	41342400.	-305856688.	76539061.	32272302.
2447680.5	44798400.	-274278337.	64021539.	26320589.
2447720.5	48254400.	-242124427.	53669931.	21285481.
2447760.5	51710400.	-209548661.	45496125.	17175731.
2447800.5	55166400.	-176703781.	39503295.	13996332.
2447840.5	58622400.	-143740953.	35686161.	11748613.
2447880.5	62078400.	-110809206.	34031248.	10430340.
2447920.5	65534400.	-78054892.	34517168.	10035819.
2447960.5	68990400.	-45621191.	37114900.	10556006.
2448000.5	72446400.	-13647646.	41788085.	11978622.
2448040.5	75902400.	17730266.	48493330.	14288275.
2448080.5	79358400.	48381525.	57180522.	17466581.
2448120.5	82814400.	78179926.	67793151.	21492295.
2448160.5	86270400.	107004401.	80268638.	26341447.
2448200.5	89726400.	134739307.	94538684.	31987483.
2448240.5	93182400.	161274676.	110529617.	38401403.
2448280.5	96638400.	186506429.	128162755.	45551918.
2448320.5	100094400.	210336560.	147354775.	53405601.
2448360.5	103550400.	232673282.	168018095.	61927046.
2448400.5	107006400.	253431132.	190061264.	71079035.
2448440.5	110462400.	272531049.	213389360.	80822706.
2448480.5	113918400.	289900414.	237904400.	91117725.
2448520.5	117374400.	305473050.	263505760.	101922471.
2448560.5	120830400.	319189194.	290090601.	113194216.
2448600.5	124286400.	330995430.	317554307.	124889314.
2448640.5	127742400.	340844584.	345790934.	136963398.
2448680.5	131198400.	348695589.	374693667.	149371580.
2448720.5	134654400.	354513310.	404155285.	162068649.
2448760.5	138110400.	358268339.	434068638.	175009289.
2448800.5	141566400.	359936747.	464327132.	188148287.
2448840.5	145022400.	359499808.	494825227.	201440752.
2448880.5	148478400.	356943683.	525458937.	214842344.
2448920.5	151934400.	352259072.	556126351.	228309498.
2448960.5	155390400.	345440827.	586728151.	241799661.
2449000.5	158846400.	336487533.	617168150.	255271530.